

Giant Magellan Telescope Active Optics Designs

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ABSTRACT

The Giant Magellan Telescope (GMT) will employ seven 8.4m primary mirror segments and seven 1m secondary mirror segments to achieve the diffraction limit of a 25.4m aperture. In order to maintain image quality, an active optics system is employed to sense and control mirror position and figure. First, we present an optical design for the Acquisition, Guide and Wavefront Sensing Subsystem (AGWS) of the active optics system that is compatible with the newly available Raptor Falcon camera. Additionally, a unique challenge of the GMT is keeping the seven pairs of primary-secondary mirror segments in phase. We then present a conceptual opto-mechanical design for a prototype dispersed fringe sensor. The prototype, which operates at J-band and incorporates an infrared avalanche photodiode array, will be deployed on the Magellan Clay Telescope to verify the sensitivity and accuracy of the planned GMT phasing sensor.

1. Introduction

The Giant Magellan Telescope is an optical and infrared telescope planned for the Las Campanas Observatory, Chile (Johns et al. 2014). The GMT is on track to finish construction in 2024 and aims to be the first of a new class of Extremely Large Telescopes (GMTO 2016). Upon completion, the GMT will have ten times the angular resolution of the Hubble Space Telescope allowing it to resolve small-scale details unobservable with current telescopes (Dressing and Fuchs 2016). With this high resolving power, the GMT will be used to explore a wide variety of astrophysics including exoplanetary systems, the formation of stars, planets, galaxies, and black holes, the origins of chemical elements, dark matter and energy, and first light and reionization shortly after the Big Bang (GMTO 2016).

The 25.4m Gregorian telescope is comprised of seven 8.4m circular primary mirrors corresponding with seven adaptive 1m secondary mirrors (Figure 1). The segmented primary mirror allows for a large effective primary aperture without the cost and manufacturing constraints of creating primary mirror greater than twenty meters in diameter. All of the

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planned Extremely Large Telescopes, including the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) and European Extremely Large Telescope (E-ELT), employ segmented primary mirror designs. The TMT and E-ELT primary mirrors will be comprised of hundreds of hexagonal 1.45m mirror segments in contrast to the GMTs seven circular segments (Dressing and Fuchs 2016). The 8.4m mirrors are more difficult to create and polish than their smaller counterparts but have been shown to work well as the primary mirrors on the MMT, Magellan, and Large Binocular Telescopes. These segments provide the largest possible continuous area for collecting light and have a well-tested manufacturing process (GMTO 2016).

Fig. 1.— The Giant Magellan Telescope Layout

In order to maintain image quality, it is necessary to precisely control the alignment and figure, or curvature, of the telescope primary and secondary mirrors (McLeod et al. 2014). A closed-loop control system of the telescope optics, referred to as active optics, is employed to correct for these variations by observing reference guide stars or lasers. The GMT active optics system senses and controls changes in the position and shape of optics, which can vary due to thermal and gravitational distortions that occur on relatively long time scales. Common causes for distortions include wind or temperature changes (GMTO).

The GMT implements active optics via three systems: sensors, mechanical controllers of optical elements, and control algorithms that link the sensors to the mechanical controllers. This report will focus on the sensors, which are a part of the Acquisition, Guide and Wavefront Sensing Subsystem (AGWS). The AGWS system is composed of four units that observe off-axis in a 20 arcminute diameter field of view, directly surrounding the 10 arcminute science field used for observing science targets (Figure 2). The AGWS units can operate in one of four modes: acquisition camera, full telescope guider, Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor

(WFS), or seven-segment tip-tilt guider (TT7). At any given time, one of these four interchangeable optical channels can be employed per AGWS unit. Typically, one sensor will operate as a segment guider and the other three as wavefront sensors (SAO 2013).

Fig. 2.— The AGWS system as viewed from below (left). Each probe has a beam-splitter that passes visible light through one of four sensor modes to a camera (right). The infrared light is passed through a dispersed fringe sensor and infrared camera behind the visible system.

In addition to guiding and active optics, the AGWS includes a subsystem for primary and secondary mirror segment phasing. Using seven pairs of mirror segments offers advantages such as a larger effective radius but also poses challenges. Each pair of mirrors must be kept in phase, at the proper distance and angle relative to each other, within a fraction of the observing wavelength so that the GMT can reach its diffraction limit (Van Dam et al. 2016). In order to measure these piston phase differences (changes in relative distance) a dispersed fringe sensor (DFS) has been proposed.

The DFS on the GMT utilizes light from 18 apertures, 12 placed on the boundaries between segments and 6 in the middle of the outer mirrors, in order to analyze the phasing of the segments. Each aperture creates a set of fringes similar to a 2-slit diffraction pattern. The fringes are then dispersed via a pair of prisms with a resultant fringe spacing that is dependent on wavelength. Consequently, any phase shift between two mirror segments will cause a tilt in the fringe pattern. In a Fourier transform, a tilt will cause a shift in the peak of the data, which then provides a measurement of piston phase difference error (Kopon et al. 2016). While the previously described optical channels operate in the visible spectrum, the phasing sensor operates in the infrared spectrum. A beam splitter is used to divert the IR light from the visible light and send it to the DFS optics wrapping around and behind the guiding and active optics system (Figure 2).

Fig. 3.— The GMT pupil with twelve 1.5m subapertures placed at each of the boundaries (left). Simulated J-band fringes indicate zero phase difference (left) and a ten micron phase difference (right).

In order to test and develop the technology needed for a DFS to operate on the GMT, a series of prototypes have been designed and tested on the Magellan Clay Telescope, a 6.5m telescope currently in operation in Chile. In 2012, a prototype operating in the K-band was successfully tested with cryogenic optics and a fast-steering mirror, both of which are no longer necessary due to recently developed sub-electron noise fast readout IR arrays such as the CRED-One avalanche photodiode array from First Light Imaging. Consequently, in 2016, a second prototype was successfully tested in the I and J-bands, but ran into some unexpected errors and biases (Kopon et al. 2016). A third prototype operating only in the J-band is under development. The prototype will build upon the previous model with some mechanical and optical changes (see section 4). The third prototype aims to demonstrate that a dispersed fringe sensor with an improved optical design and a newly available detector can effectively function as a GMT phasing sensor.

2. Methods

I learned to use the ray-tracing optics software *Zemax* for both the camera feasibility and dispersed fringe sensor projects. For the camera feasibility project, I redesigned four optical channels based on previous designs by D. Kopon that are intended to work with the Andor iXon Ultra 897 camera. I placed constraints on each design in order to specify requirements such as effective focal length, total distance, and minimum thickness, and optimized each

design using built-in least-squares fit functions. Spot diagrams produced by *Zemax* were used for feasibility analysis. For the dispersed fringe sensor project, I also worked with designs by D. Kopon intended for the GMT and fit them to the constraints of the Magellan telescope. In addition to the optical design, I worked on initial ideas for the mechanical design of the third DFS prototype in *SolidWorks* based on the design for the second DFS prototype by K. McCracken.

3. AGWS Camera Feasibility

The camera used for the guide and active optics subsystem of the AGWS has the unique challenge of meeting requirements for four different optical channels. The acquisition and guide channels needs a large field of view, the TT7 channel requires a high frame rate but a smaller field of view, and the WFS channel operates with a low frame and produces full-frame images. These requirements lead to a limited number of viable cameras (SAO 2013). The current system is designed to be compatible with the Andor iXon Ultra 897, which was the best choice available at the time of the initial AGWS design. An alternative sensor, the e2v CCD351, was recently developed and a new camera employing the sensor is expected to be on the market in the coming year. The new sensor is expected to achieve faster readout rates at higher performance than the e2v CCD201, the sensor used in the Andor iXon Ultra 897 camera. The new e2v CCD351 operates at a 37Mhz pixel rate, nerly twice the rate of the previous sensor, and has smaller pixels of $10\mu m^2$ (Jordan et al. 2016). One of the goals of this project is to redesign the optics of the four optical channels to see if the Raptor Falcon camera is feasible for use on the AGWS system of the GMT.

Due to the higher resolution of the Raptor Falcon, the optical prescription must be updated in each channel to account for the consequent change in magnification. The current camera detector is comprised of 1024x1024 square pixels, each with an area of $13\mu m^2$, while the new camera is expected to have 1024x1024 square pixels with an area of $10\mu m^2$. For this project, each mode was redesigned with a shorter effective focal length so that the correct final magnification can be imaged onto the new camera detector. In order to correct for variations in the incoming wavefront on the order of 0.5 arcseconds ("), each mode must resolve point sources to a spot radius of 0.1".

3.1. Acquisition

The initial-acquisition mode is used for quick imaging of a guide star for coarse measurements or faint guide stars. The acquisition function has a 30" x 30" wide field of view (FOV) for imaging large portions of the sky. In order to account for new $10\mu m^2$ pixels instead of the previous $13\mu m^2$ pixels, the effective focal length of the redesigned acquisition channel is scaled by 10/13 for a new focal length of 70402mm (Figure 4, Table 1).

To obtain a maximum spot radius of 0.1", the optics were optimized using a built-in Hammer Current optimization function and analyzed by plotting the full-width half-max spot radii on and off-axis (Figure 5). The resultant spot radii range from approximately 10 to $18\mu m$, which correspond to approximately 0.03" and 0.05" in a 30" FOV, both less than the target 0.1". The subsequent optical prescription of the redesigned system is detailed in table 1.

Fig. 4.— Optical layout of the original design (top) and redesigned (bottom) acquisition channel with a shorter focal length to meet the new detector resolution.

Fig. 5.— Spot diagram for the acquisition channel showing the RMS with respect to the chief ray on-axis (upper left), 10.4'' off-axis (upper right), and 15.1'' degrees off-axis (bottom).

Surface	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material
10	Focus	-2197.173	0.000	
11	Field Lens	Infinity	-9.086	N-BAF51
12	Field Lens	174.687	-99.205	
13	Lens group 1	-964.507	-5.653	P-LASF50
14	Lens group 1	-36.952	-14.576	N-BAF5
15	Lens group 1	270.134	-54.318	
16	Lens group 2	-107.335	-10.069	N-LAK33B
17	Lens group 2	49.678	-2.443	LAFN7
18	Lens group 2	264.902	-58.425	
19	Lens group 2	Infinity	-2.125	
20	Lens group 3	-40.276	-17.64	N-SK4
21	Lens group 3	34.433	-5.057	N-SF57
22	Lens group 3	131.809	-41.779	
23	Detector	Infinity	-	

Table 1: Lens data for the acquisition channel including radius, thickness, and material for each surface.

3.2. Guide

The guide mode functions similarly to the acquisition mode but with a smaller 3.2” FOV with and an 8x8 pixel binning. Consequently, the guide mode has a faster readout rate. The effective focal length is also reduced by 10/13 (Figure 6). With the previous number of lenses and restrictions on the optics, a system with a focal reduced by 10/13 did not yield a spot size smaller than 1/10”. Consequently, we added two extra lenses to meet both effective focal length and prescribed spot size. See the appendix for the optical prescription and spot radius diagram (Figure 12, Table 4).

Fig. 6.— Optical layout of the original design (top) and redesigned (bottom) guide channel with a shorter focal length and two new lenses to meet the prescribed spot size. Note the direction of the light path is opposite to Figure 5.

3.3. Wavefront System

The wavefront sensor (WFS) is employed to determine the shape of an incoming wave of light distorted primarily by the atmosphere. Information on the wavefront’s shape is then sent to control algorithms and mechanical actuators on the mirrors that compensate for the distortions, ultimately producing a flat wavefront. In order to image the shape of the wavefront, and therefore characterize optical aberrations, the WFS employs a Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor. In the WFS channel, an array of 48x48 small lenses (called a lenslet array) splits and refocuses the primary column of light into thousands of individual images, each with its own central reference point. The displacement of each discrete image from its reference point corresponds to the local tilt of the wavefront (Figure 7)(Woods 2009). Across 48x48 subapertures, this provides the control algorithms with enough information to recreate the wavefront shape.

Fig. 7.— An example array of images created by the Shack-Hartmann wavefront sensor which provide information of the local tilt of the wavefront at each point. This image illustrates 24x24 subapertures, fewer than the 48x48 subapertures created in the WFS channel.

The WFS in the AGWS passes light from the telescope focus through a collimator, creating parallel rays which form an image of the telescope pupil on the lenslet array. The lenslet array then forms 48x48 images of the star, each displaced based on wavefront distortions. The relay lenses reimages this pattern onto the camera (Figure 8).

Each subaperture spans eight 0.4” square pixels on the detector yielding a FOV of 3.2” per subaperture. Like in the acquisition and guide channels, the new effective focal length is constrained to be 10/13 of the previous focal length. Three different redesigns are presented below based on commercially available Shack-Hartmann lenslet arrays (Figure 8). The first design presents an ideal lenslet array that matches exactly the pitch (width of each lenslet) and focal length needed for the prescribed constraints. This set of specifications is not commercially available and would require purchasing a custom lenslet array. Two commercially

available arrays are also analyzed (Table 6). The first, sold by SUSS MicroOptics, has a FOV of 0.32” per pixel, which was ultimately deemed too low compared to the goal of 0.4” per pixel. The second lenslet array, sold by Advanced MicroOptic Systems, has the correct FOV but would be too large for the current tube encasing the optical channel. See the appendix for the optical prescription and spot radius diagram (Figure 15, Table 6).

Manufacturer	Pitch (μm)	Lenslet Focal Length (mm)	Collimator Focal Length (mm)	Resolution (”/pix)
Custom	80	0.768	30.72	0.4
SUSS	222	1.681	85.248	0.4
AMS	110	1.788	42.24	0.32

Table 2: Data on the custom, SUSS MicroOptics, and Advanced MicroOptic Systems options for a lenslet array to be used in the WFS mode.

Fig. 8.— Top to bottom: Optical layout of the WFS channel before, the redesigned channel with a custom, SUSS MicroOptics, and Advanced MicroOptic Systems lenslet array.

3.4. Tip-Tilt 7

The seven-element Shack-Hartmann tip-tilt sensor (TT7) mode provides the ability to obtain acquisition and guide images from each of the seven mirror segments. The TT7 channel works similarly to the WFS with a seven-lenslet array instead of the 48x48 array. Light from the telescope focus is collimated and an image of the telescope pupil (consisting of seven segments) is imaged onto the lenslet array. The seven lenslets produce an image for each of the seven mirror segments, providing information on the tipping and tilting of the segments. The two groups of relay lenses pass the seven images of the star onto the camera. The TT7 mode has a 15" FOV for each subaperture and a 4x4 binning of each pixel, corresponding to a $52\mu\text{m}$ pixel. For the new camera, each pixel will be 5x5 binned, corresponding to a $50\mu\text{m}$ pixel. Consequently, the effective focal length in the redesign was scaled by a factor of 50/52 (Figure 9). See the appendix for the optical prescription and spot radius diagram (Figure 14, Table 5).

Fig. 9.— Optical layout of the original design (top) and redesigned (bottom) guide channel with a shorter effective focal length.

3.5. Camera Feasibility Summary

All four AGWS mode redesigns successfully met the prescribed criteria and consequently the Raptor Faclon camera is a feasible option for use on the GMT. In each channel, the effective focal length was successfully constrained to fit the resolution of the new camera and the resultant spot radii met the prescribed constraint.

Channel	Focal Length (mm)	Binning Factor	Collimator FL (mm)	Lenslet FL (mm)	Relay Magnification	Final Pixel Scale ("/pix)
Acquisition	70402	1x1	-	-	2.93	0.0293
Guide	44003	8x8	-	-	3.125	0.3750
Wavefront	5125	1x1	30.72	0.768	40.00	0.4025
TT7	25783	5x5	47.1307	6.0807	1.465	0.4000

Table 3: Summary of optical properties for the camera feasibility design for the Acquisition, Guide, Wavefront, and TT7 channels.

4. Dispersed Fringe Sensor Prototype

4.1. Optical Design

The DFS prototype will operate in the J-band in order to measure the distance between segments in a variety of modes. In order to simulate the GMT phasing system on the Magellan telescope, which only has one primary and secondary mirror, we overlay three segment boundary apertures on the Magellan telescope pupil. In the basic design of the prototype, light from the telescope is collimated to create an image of the Magellan telescope’s pupil and overlay it on an aperture mask. The light is split into three images via a hexagonal lenslet array and spread into fringes using a pair of prisms. The consequent dispersed fringe patterns for each subaperture are then able to be imaged and analyzed.

The DFS can operate in a variety of modes via three optical trains that offer a selection of optics. The first allows for the choice of imaging the star or the telescope pupil. The next offers a choice between using the prisms or obtaining an unobscured image. The final train allows for off-axis or on-axis imaging. When imaging off-axis, the Magellan telescope has significant coma and astigmatism, a problem not present in the GMT optics. In order to properly measure phase, an interchangeable Off-Axis Lens assembly is used to statically correct for coma and astigmatism.

Fig. 10.— The optical design of the DFS J-band channel. Movable stages will allow for the selection of on or off-axis modes, prism or unobscured modes, and image or pupil viewing modes.

4.2. Mechanical Design

Once the optics are successfully designed, they will be fit into a mechanical design. The mechanical design of the DFS prototype will be modeled heavily off of the previous prototype with a few major adjustments. The largest changes that need to be redesigned include the interchangeable optical trains needed to integrate the variety of imaging modes mentioned above, and accommodating a new camera. The DFS will employ a newly available infrared avalanche photodiode array: C-RED One by First-Light Imaging. A major design change will involve constraining the optical design to the camera specifications and mechanically accommodating a larger camera and optical train.

Fig. 11.— The new CRED photodiode array camera (purple) overlain on the previous DFS prototype. Left: the camera mounted next to the previous two cameras used in the previous DFS prototype mounted in the same style as the smaller cameras. Right: the camera tilted upward to concentrate more of the camera’s mass closer to the center of the prototype.

4.3. Conclusions and Future Work

Most of the work on the latest DFS prototype has yet to be completed. Future work will include finishing the optical and mechanical designs of the prototype and then building it over the course of the coming year and testing it on the Magellan Clay Telescope.

5. Acknowledgements

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6. Appendix

6.1. Guide

Fig. 12.— Spot diagram for the guide channel showing the RMS with respect to the chief ray on-axis (upper left), 10.4'' off-axis (upper right), and 15.1'' degrees off-axis (bottom).

Surface	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material
8	Focus	2197.173	17	
9	Beam Splitter	Infinity	10	CAF2
10	Beam Splitter	Infinity	16.299	
11	Lens Group 1	-59.343	8	N-KZFS4HT
12	Lens Group 1	19.87	8	N-LASF45HT
13	Lens Group 1	1.27E+04	189.362	
14	Lens Group 2	112.797	9.01	N-LAF21
15	Lens Group 2	-28.964	2.094	SF57
16	Lens Group 2	-147.664	2.154	
17	Pupil	Infinity	2.08	
18	Lens Group 3	40.86	8	LFHTI
19	Lens Group 3	-52.728	8	LASF35
20	Lens Group 3	-116.175	40	
21	Detector	Infinity	-	

Table 4: Lens data for the guide channel including radius, thickness, and material for each surface.

6.2. TT7

Fig. 13.— Three TT7 optical configurations corresponding to light passing through one of the three middle lenslets in the seven-element lenslet array.

Surface	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material
8	Focus	2197.173	37.915	
9	Collimator	34.021	5.00	N-LASF..
10	Collimator	17.264	12.00	N-PK52A
11	Collimator	-21.361	5.00	N-ZK7
12	Collimator	-29.828	40.42	
13	Collimator	Infinity	0.00	
15	Lenslet	Infinity	1.00	S-TIH53
16	Lenslet	-0.166	6.081	
18	Int. focus	Infinity	25.16	
19	Relay Lens 1	5.28E+04	8.071	SK10
20	Relay Lens 1	-39.725	3.171	
21	Relay Lens 1	58.9	12.998	N-SF66
22	Relay Lens 2	24.078	22.564	SSK4A
23	Relay Lens 2	-78.808	63.504	
24	Relay Lens 2	100.234	13.416	SSK4A
25	Relay Lens 3	-25.977	10.644	N-SF66
26	Relay Lens 3	-68.294	5.262	
27	Relay Lens 3	39.656	7.794	SK10
28	Relay Lens 3	-524.951	40.00	
29	Detector	Infinity	0.00	

Table 5: Lens data for the TT7 channel including radius, thickness, and material for each surface.

Fig. 14.— Spot diagram for the TT7 channel showing the RMS with respect to the chief ray on-axis (upper left), 10.4'' off-axis (upper right), and 15.1'' degrees off-axis (bottom).

6.3. Wavefront System

Fig. 15.— Spot diagram for the WFS channel showing the RMS with respect to the chief ray on-axis (upper left), 10.4° off-axis (upper right), and 15.1° degrees off-axis (bottom).

Surface	Comment	Radius	Thickness	Material
9	Focus	Infinity	10.000	
10	Beam Splitter	Infinity	7.073	CAF2
11	Beam Splitter	26.595	5.999	
12	Collimator	-1450.442	5.997	N-PSK57
13	Collimator	-56.162	30.72	KZFS12
15	Lenslet	Infinity	1.000	-
16	Lenslet	-1.536	1.681	-
18	Internal Focus	Infinity	6.552	LAF2
19	Relay Lens 1	86.727	4.358	N-SF57
20	Relay Lens 1	-12.245	2.951	
21	Relay Lens 1	-30.379	181.901	N-SF57
22	Relay Lens 2	30.379	2.951	LAF2
23	Relay Lens 2	12.245	2.358	
24	Relay Lens 2	-86.727	40.869	
25	Detector	Infinity	-	

Table 6: Lens data for the WFS channel including radius, thickness, and material for each surface.

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